

INTERDEPENDENCE OF THE MAJOR WORLD STOCK EXCHANGES: AFTER GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS

* Dinesh Thapak,

* *Phd, Research Scholar, R.K. University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India*

***Changani Jagdish*

PGDRM, MHRD Department, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University Surat, Gujarat, India.

Abstract

Vector Auto-regression Model (VAR) has recently become a popular tool for economic analysis and forecasting for multivariate co-integrated time series. In the context of globalization, through a growing process of economic integration among countries and financial markets, the interdependency among major world financial markets is more than evident. The paper covers the After Global crises period 2009-2013 using weekly based data and investigates and examines the short and long-run relationships between major world financial markets with particular attention to the Greek stock exchange. The research methodology employed includes testing for stationarity, both with the Dickey- Fuller and the Phillips-Perron tests, the use of a VAR (Proc VARMAX) in SAS® model for the implementation of the Granger Causality test, and Co-integration tests according to Johansen-Juselious. The results confirm the dominance of the USA financial market and the strong influence of DAX and FTSE on all other markets of the sample. The influence of Germany and the DJ index is especially noticeable on the Athens stock exchange. We conduct co-integration tests with variance decomposition and estimate the impulse response functions. This paper demonstrates these techniques using SAS®/ETS 9.22 forecasting software. The comparison generated from the program helps us to decide the best forecasting method.

Key Word: *Market Interdependency, Variance decomposition, VAR Model, Visual analytics*

*Corresponding author: ***Changani Jagdish*

Reference this paper as: Dinesh Thapak & Jagdish .G (2014). “Interdependence of the Major World Stock Exchanges: After Global Financial Crisis,” *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, Vol. 2, Issue 1, Jan-Feb-2014, pp 01-16,*

Introduction:

In the current era of globalization and liberalization along with technological advancement the entire globe is now a very small village where the news spread with a lighting speed and the effects of the same in the home country and overseas is clearly visible in a short span of time. Globalization had increased the base of investment of the investors in equity and other equity related instruments from their home country to the other part of the world in different indices. They can now earn more return by diversifying their portfolio with a mixture of stocks from the various indices across the sphere.

Table 1: Summary of major Stock Exchanges and Stock Indices under Investigation

Name	Amsterdam Exchange index	Brussels Stock Exchange	Paris Stock Exchange or Cotation Assistée en Continu (Continuous Assisted Quotation)	German stock index(Deutscher Aktien Index)	S&P Dow Jones Indices	FTSE 100 Index or footsie	Athens Stock Exchange	Nikkei 225 or Nikkei
Abbreviation	AEX	BEL20	CAC40	DAX	S&P DJA	FTSE100	ASE or ATHEX	Nikkei 225
Head quarter	Amsterdam	Amsterdam	Amsterdam	Frankfurt	55 Water Street, New York	London	Athens	Tokyo
Country	Netheland(Dutch)	Belgian	France	Germany	United States	United Kingdom	Greece	Japan
Foundation	1983	30-Dec-90	1987	1-Jul-88	1882	1984	1876	1878
Operator	Euronext	Euronext	Euronext	Deutsche Börse	S&P Dow Jones Indices	FTSE Group	HELEX Group	Japan Exchange Group, Inc
Exchanges	Euronext Amsterdam	Euronext Brussel	Euronext Paris	Frankfurt Stock Exchange	New York Stock Exchange NASDAQ	London Stock Exchange[Athens Stock Exchange	Japan Exchange Group, Inc
Constituents	25 companies	25 companies	40 companies	30 companies	500+30 companies	101 companies	317 companies	225 companies
Type	Large cap	Large cap	Large cap	Large cap	Large cap	Large cap	Large cap	Large cap
Market cap (USD bn)	2,930	300	1,823	1,486	14,085	3,396	45	3,478

Weighting method	Market value-weighted	Market value-weighted	Capitalization-weighted	Capitalization-weighted	Capitalization-weighted & Price-weighted	Capitalization-weighted	Capitalization-weighted	Capitalization-weighted
Related indices	AMX index, AScX index		CAC Next 20, CAC Mid 60, CAC Small	MDAX, SDAX, TecDAX, ÖkoDAX	S&P 500, Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJIA)	FTSE 250, FTSE 350, FTSE Small Cap, FTSE All-Share, FTSE Fledgling, FTSE AIM UK 50 Index	ASE 317	Nikkei 225, TOPIX
Operation time	9.00-17.30, CET/CEST (Central European Time/Central European Summer Time) +1	9.00-17.30, CET/CEST (Central European Time/Central European Summer Time) +1	9.00-17.30, CET/CEST (Central European Time/Central European Summer Time) +2	8.00-22.00, CET/CEST (Central European Time/Central European Summer Time) +3	9:30-16:00 EST/EDT (Eastern Time/Daylight Time) -5	8:00-16:30 GMT/BST (Greenwich Mean Time/Britain Summer Time)	10:00-17:20 EET (Eastern Time) +2	9:00-15:00 JST (Japan Standard Time) +9
Website	www.nyse.com	www.indices.nyx.com	www.nyse.com/cac40	www.deutsche-boerse.com	www.djindexes.com or www.spindices.com	www.ftse.com	www.athex.gr	www.tse.or.jp

Literature Review

Currently interdependence among the stock exchanges has been widely examined. Early studies have pointed out that the degree of interdependence of share price movements among the market is an insignificant and the major determinants are the domestic factors rather than international. In recent years, the capital inflow and outflow are almost free among the countries. At the same time, transmission of information has become faster than before due to the wider advancement of technological and applications. As a result, higher price movements in the stock markets are experiencing and exhibit a substantial degree of interdependence among stock markets.

Table 2: Literature Review

The summary of literature review is tablets below:

Study	Markets Under Study	Period of S	Methodology	Results Found

			t u d y		
	Eun and Shim (1989)	USA, UK, Canada, Germany, France, Australia, Japan, Switzerland and Hong Kong	1980-1985	VAR to the daily closing price data	They did not find evidence that the foreign market can explained the price movements in the US market.
	Malliaris and Urrutia (1992)	USA, UK, Australia, Hong-Kong, Japan and Singapore	March 1988	Granger Causality test to examine the direction of causality.	They concluded that the USA was no more the world dominant market.
	Kwan et al. (1995)	Australia, Hong Kong, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, UK, USA, and Germany	1982-1991	Investigated long-run relationship using co-integration analysis	They found that these markets were not weak form efficient.
	Elyasiani et al.	USA, Japan, India, Hong Kong, South	1998	VAR technique	They did not detect any causal relationship between Sri

	(1998)	Korea, Taiwan, Singapore and Sri Lanka	January 1989 to June 1994	for daily data	Lanka and its trading partners and also indicated that dynamic responses to external shocks were very low. Therefore, they concluded that there was no significant interdependence between Sri Lanka and other equity markets.
	Siklos and Ng (2001)	USA, Japan, Hong Kong, Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand		Cointegration Tests	Single common stochastic trend among Asian and North American markets is a recent phenomenon. The 1987 stock market crash was significant. The 1991 Gulf War also signalled a turning point in the degree of stock market integration among the countries studied
	Yan and Lim (200	Hong Kong, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia,	1990	VAR Technique, Cointeg	Substantial increase in the degree of interdependence after the 1997 crisis.

	2)	Thailand, Philippines, Singapore, Taiwan, Japan	- 2 0 0 0	ration Tests, Standar d correlati on tests, Granger causalit y test	Taiwan is very independent from other markets. Capital controls may have an impact on the inter-relationships between stock markets in the region
	Bose (200 5)	Hong Kong, Korea, Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, India, USA, Japan	1 9 9 - 2 0 0 4	Cointeg ration Tests, Stationa ry Tests, Granger Causalit y	Post-Asian crisis and up to mid-2004, the Indian stock market did not function in relative isolation from the rest of Asia and the US as stock returns in India were highly correlated with returns in major Asian markets and was led by returns in the US, Japan, as well as other Asian markets
	Glez akos et al. (200 7)	USA, Japan, UK, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, Holland, Belgium, and Greece	2 0 0 0 - 2 0 0	VAR method ology to test short and long- run	The results showed that the USA market is the dominance market in the world, while influence of the Germany and UK also substantial on all other

			6	relation ship	markets of the sample.
	Gkle zako u and Myl onak is (200 9)	Developing stock markets of the South Eastern Europe.	2 0 0 - 2 0 0 9	Granger causalit y test to analyze the daily closing price data	Their finding indicate that the interdependence of the stock exchanges were strong during the current economic crisis.
	Gkle zako u and Myl onak is (201 0)	USA, Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain, the United Kingdom and Japan.	2 0 0 0 t o 2 0 0 9	Interdep endence among ten markets using daily closing price	The empirical findings indicated that the recent economic recession leads to enhance their correlation, and tightened their existing relations. Moreover, they found that while the direction of influence seems to be increased during the crisis, the leading role of the USA and Germany were confirmed.
	Dars han Ran pura et al. (201 1)	India and Japan	J u l y 1 9 9 7 t o D e c e m b e r	Co- movem ent and interdep endence	They found that the SENSEX has given highest Risk adjusted return for the whole period followed by BVSP, whereas Nikkei has given negative Risk adjusted return for the same period. They also found that that SENSEX is interdependent on Developed countries stock markets except NIKKEI.

			2 0 0 9		
	Mallika A. K. Sriyalatha, Hiroshi Torii and Michio Kuniyama (2012)	USA, Germany, UK, Japan, Singapore and Sri Lanka	1 9 9 0 - 2 0 1 0	Vector Autoregressive (VAR) and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to identify co-integration and causal link between the price indices.	They found that under the context of globalization, the stock markets are enhanced their interrelations after the recent economic recession. Especially an emerging market of Sri Lanka is affected by almost all developed markets during the post-economic recession. Meanwhile, the leading role of the US market in the world stock market is clearly visible throughout all causality tests and in all time periods.
	Nikunj R. Patel, Sushil Mohanty and Neeta Pathak (2012)	US, Japan, UK, Germany, France, Australia, Brazil, China, Malaysia, Hong Kong, Korea, Pakistan and India	J a n u a r y 2 0 0 1 o M a y 2 0	correlation and Granger - causality tests	The degree of integration found is not significant that implies the nature of integration with emerging Asian markets does not yet warrant any immediate concern for India regarding possible contagion effect. The observations also showed that there is still much scope for reaping benefits of portfolio diversification.

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Objective of the Study:

- Is there interdependency among financial markets and if there is what is the direction of causality (short-run effects)
- Is there a long-run relationship among markets?
- What does the variance decomposition show in the case of market inter dependency and also estimation of the impulse response functions to determine the time period required to restore equilibrium, after an external shock hits the market.

Data; The Sample

The general stock indices of the countries which make up the sample of the present study. They were chosen for the following reasons.

- The USA by general concession is the strongest financial market worldwide
- The Japanese market is one of the strongest worldwide and the leader in the Asia region
- England, France and Germany have the strongest European markets
- The Italian and the Spanish markets are the most dynamic in the Mediterranean region, part of which is the Greek financial market
- Belgium and Holland are two dynamic countries but rather of small size like Greece.

Table 3: Stock Exchanges and Stock Indices under Investigation

Country	Index	
USA	DJI	Dow Jones
ENGLAND	FTSE	FTSE – 100
FRANCE	CAC	France Cac 40
GERMANY	DAX	Dax 30 Performance
BELGIUM	BEL	Bel 20
HOLLAND	HOL	Aex Index
GREECE	GEN	Athens General
JAPAN	NIKKEI	Nikkei 225

The timing of daily operations among the different stock exchanges do not coincide, therefore during the evaluation of our results we must consider the differences among the daily running of different stock exchanges

The research covers the After Global crises time period April 2009 to September 2013 and in total we have at our disposal weekly based prices for each one of the indices. In the cases that a stock exchange remains closed, the price of the relevant index is calculated by simulation for the particular day. The data are provided by the data base of Finance Yahoo. The use of daily prices was chosen because the weekly or monthly intervals might be large enough so that do not allow the underpinning of interrelations that conclude within one or only a few days (Stivaktakis et.al., 2006).

Methodology

In the context of the methodology employed for the purposes of the current study we undertake:

- Testing for stationarity, both with the Dickey- Fuller and the Phillips-Perron tests.
- Using a VAR model for the implementation of the Granger Causality test, aims to identify interdependency between financial markets in the short-run.
- Cointegration tests as they were put forward by Johansen-Juselious, for pinpointing the longrun relationships among the financial markets under investigation. The purpose is to grasp the mechanism of influence exertion. In this context we use the Engle-Granger and Johansen tests as well as the error correction model –ECM, which allows disequilibrium correction and the attainment of long-run equilibrium.
- Variance Decomposition and estimating the Impulse Response Functions.

Estimation and Analysis of Empirical Results:

During the period under examination, most markets showed positive returns (with the exceptions of the Athens Stock Exchange (Athens Stock Exchange)), the highest return came from the Dow

Jones. During the same period GEN(Greece Market) showed the highest volatility and Dow Jones the lowest, while the FTSE 100 Index moves within average levels of risk and return.

The values of asymmetry and kurtosis shown on Table 4 suggest that the sample stock returns are not normally distributed.

Table 4: Characteristics of Distributions of the Stock Indices Under Investigation

	<i>AEX</i>	<i>BEL</i>	<i>CAC</i>	<i>DAX</i>	<i>DJI</i>	<i>FTSE</i>	<i>GEN</i>	<i>N225</i>
Mean	0.0023	0.0024	0.0020	0.0034	0.0028	0.0024	-0.0005	0.0025
Standard Error	0.0018	0.0018	0.0019	0.0019	0.0014	0.0015	0.0031	0.0018
Median	0.0022	0.0059	0.0049	0.0055	0.0040	0.0033	0.0020	0.0033
Standard Deviation	0.0275	0.0271	0.0297	0.0289	0.0211	0.0225	0.0482	0.0283
Sample Variance	0.0008	0.0007	0.0009	0.0008	0.0004	0.0005	0.0023	0.0008
Kurtosis	1.7574	1.6971	1.3494	2.2492	1.0568	2.0817	-0.0454	0.7811
Skewness	-0.0963	-0.4155	-0.3494	-0.4050	0.0035	-0.3638	-0.0735	-0.1520
Minimum	-0.0998	-0.1032	-0.1112	-0.1289	-0.0641	-0.0977	-0.1281	-0.1022
Maximum	0.0962	0.0885	0.1078	0.1070	0.0733	0.0751	0.1371	0.1036
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.0035	0.0035	0.0038	0.0037	0.0027	0.0029	0.0061	0.0036

Table 5 shows the return correlations among the various indices. We deduce the following:

- Generally, the correlations among the returns of the countries under investigation are high, this is a first indication for the existence of interdependency among them
- The highest of correlations is among Germany and France (over 92%) and the lowest among Greece(Athens) and Tokyo (about 12%).It must also be pointed out that the Tokyo stock exchange.

Table 5: Correlations of Returns of the Stock Indices Under Investigation

	<i>AEX</i>	<i>BEL</i>	<i>CAC</i>	<i>DAX</i>	<i>DJI</i>	<i>FTSE</i>	<i>GEN</i>	<i>N225</i>
AEX	1	0.862127	0.906589	0.879748	0.811929	0.879706	0.481442	0.486055
BEL	0.862127	1	0.909015	0.856455	0.773576	0.851009	0.52725	0.507632
CAC	0.906589	0.909015	1	0.91918	0.846028	0.900878	0.539594	0.561054

DAX	0.879748	0.856455	0.91918	1	0.825447	0.85819	0.493662	0.542841
DJI	0.811929	0.773576	0.846028	0.825447	1	0.851636	0.433653	0.524131
FTSE	0.879706	0.851009	0.900878	0.85819	0.851636	1	0.498786	0.550192
GEN	0.481442	0.52725	0.539594	0.493662	0.433653	0.498786	1	0.398071
N225	0.486055	0.507632	0.561054	0.542841	0.524131	0.550192	0.398071	1

It appears from Tables ----, which show the results of the Dickey-Fuller (ADF test), that the time-series are stationary.

Table 6: ADF Test on the Levels of the Series (lnPt)

In pt level	Lag length P	ADF Statistic	P-Value	LM tex X2 statistic	P-value
AEX	0	-17.48283	0	1.469023	0.1432
BEL	0	-19.4362	0	1.684787	0.0934
CAC	0	-16.96711	0	1.136016	0.2571
DAX	0	-16.8715	0	1.95306	0.052
DJI	0	-16.66358	0	2.212284	0.0279
FTSE	0	-16.30168	0	1.772389	0.0776
GEN	0	-14.44834	0	-0.239313	0.8111
N225	0	-14.4654	0	1.207797	0.2283

The critical values from MacKinnon (1996) for rejection of H0

Test critical values:	1% level	5% level	10% level
Trend & intercept	-3.997083	-3.428819	-3.13785
Intercept	-3.457747	-2.873492	-2.57322
None	-2.574714	-1.942164	-1.61581

4.1 Phillips-Perron Test

The Phillips-Perron test is less restrictive and provides an alternative way for checking the stationarity of a time-series. Tables 7 that follow present the results for the variables in levels. We make the same conclusions that we did with the Dickey-Fuller tests.

Table 7: Phillips-Perron test on the Levels of the Series (lnPt)

In pt level	Bandwidth	PP test statistic	P-Value	LM tex X2 statistic	P-value
AEX	7	-17.61557	0.0000	1.469023	0.1432
BEL	2	-19.38207	0.0000	1.684787	0.0934
CAC	4	-16.97003	0.0000	1.136016	0.2571
DAX	3	-16.80755	0.0000	1.95306	0.052
DJI	12	-17.17891	0.0000	2.212284	0.0279
FTSE	11	-16.57168	0.0000	1.772389	0.0776
GEN	5	-14.6048	0.0000	-0.239313	0.8111
N225	7	-14.43762	0.0000	1.207797	0.2283

Variance Decomposition of forecast errors

The variance decomposition of the stock indices under investigation is based on the analysis of responses of the variables to shocks. According to this analysis, when there is a shock through the error term we study the influence of this shock to the other variables of the system. So, we collect information for the percentage of the error variance in predicting the prices of an index which is interpreted by some other variable of the system. Also we collect information, about the time horizon within which the whole influence is completed. This way we deduce information for the importance of the influence of each variable, on all other variables of the VAR model.

It must be mentioned that the variance decomposition is affected by the ordering of the variables. In this study the stock indices are ordered by descending order of their respective markets.

The results of variance decomposition for all stock indices of the sample can be summarized as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_{1t} \\ y_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} A_{11}^{(1)} & A_{12}^{(1)} & \cdots & A_{1n}^{(1)} \\ A_{21}^{(1)} & A_{22}^{(1)} & \cdots & A_{2n}^{(1)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{n1}^{(1)} & A_{n2}^{(1)} & \cdots & A_{nn}^{(1)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{1t-1} \\ y_{2t-1} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt-1} \end{bmatrix} + \cdots + \begin{bmatrix} A_{11}^{(p)} & A_{12}^{(p)} & \cdots & A_{1n}^{(p)} \\ A_{21}^{(p)} & A_{22}^{(p)} & \cdots & A_{2n}^{(p)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{n1}^{(p)} & A_{n2}^{(p)} & \cdots & A_{nn}^{(p)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{1t-p} \\ y_{2t-p} \\ \vdots \\ y_{nt-p} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1t} \\ \varepsilon_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ \varepsilon_{nt} \end{bmatrix}$$

The framework is to compare out-of-sample forecasting performance and derive the impulse response function from the selected model. A p^{th} - order vector auto-regression, denoted

$$\Delta y_t = \begin{pmatrix} 0.00051 \\ 0.00022 \\ -0.00046 \\ 0.00001 \\ -0.00024 \\ -0.00004 \\ -0.00023 \\ 0.00009 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -0.62069 & -0.41839 & 0.92364 & -0.16774 & 0.04920 & 0.15934 & -0.00154 & -0.02604 \\ -0.40417 & -0.27244 & 0.60144 & -0.10923 & 0.03204 & 0.10376 & -0.00101 & -0.01696 \\ 0.30571 & 0.20607 & -0.45493 & 0.08262 & -0.02423 & -0.07848 & 0.00076 & 0.01283 \\ -0.14934 & -0.10067 & 0.22223 & -0.04036 & 0.01184 & 0.03834 & -0.00037 & -0.00627 \\ 0.07617 & 0.05134 & -0.11334 & 0.02058 & -0.00604 & -0.01955 & 0.00019 & 0.00320 \\ 0.00799 & 0.00539 & -0.01189 & 0.00216 & -0.00063 & -0.00205 & 0.00002 & 0.00034 \\ -0.08010 & -0.05399 & 0.11920 & -0.02165 & 0.00635 & 0.02056 & -0.00020 & -0.00336 \\ -0.09434 & -0.06359 & 0.14038 & -0.02549 & 0.00748 & 0.02422 & -0.00023 & -0.00396 \end{pmatrix} Y_{t-1} + \begin{pmatrix} -0.33985 & 0.03974 & -0.30431 & 0.01881 & 0.28996 & -0.15547 & 0.01514 & -0.03972 \\ 0.13413 & -0.52176 & -0.05490 & -0.01814 & 0.20999 & -0.34970 & 0.02458 & -0.04955 \\ -0.22603 & -0.31068 & 0.03342 & -0.13422 & 0.23837 & -0.16785 & 0.00288 & -0.06024 \\ 0.01045 & -0.16849 & 0.07034 & -0.55274 & 0.26778 & -0.16666 & 0.00399 & -0.03489 \\ -0.19099 & -0.23346 & 0.21342 & -0.05734 & -0.23914 & -0.02497 & 0.02398 & -0.01459 \\ -0.08137 & -0.08684 & 0.20396 & -0.16774 & 0.24685 & -0.59733 & 0.01680 & -0.03560 \\ 0.21517 & -0.41805 & 0.27708 & -0.12010 & 0.30132 & -0.11814 & -0.53516 & -0.08357 \\ 0.07458 & -0.33703 & 0.21304 & -0.01654 & 0.14108 & -0.00751 & 0.01251 & -0.50564 \end{pmatrix} \Delta Y_{t-1} + E_t$$

Impulse Response Analysis

The impulse response analysis investigates the influence on the markets of the sample that a random shock might have. A change in the market I for example, will not only affect market I, but it will transmit to other markets, even with a time lag.

So, the impulse response functions show the effect that a random (unpredicted) shock which occurs through one of the errors (innovations), has on the current and future index prices.

The coefficients determining the size of the response of each market to shocks in individual markets (for each period) are derived from the coefficients of the VAR model which we can only estimate. So, these response coefficients are also liable to statistical error. To evaluate the response of each market to an unforeseen change in others, it is useful to estimate confidence intervals.

From our analysis, it appears that a shock in the Dow Jones index, equal to one standard deviation in size, influences the prediction error of the Athens stock exchange to a substantial extent and the influence is completed after nine days. Nevertheless, these influences are liable to a large error and are statistically significant therefore only the first day after the shock. Therefore, the influence of a shock which occurs in the New York market, on the Other Stock Index, is completed within a day.

Also, domestic market shocks cause reactions, which last for seven days, but after the first day die gradually out, a fact which confirms the theory of finance, when it states that any event of economic nature is immediately reflected in the stock exchange. Investigating the interdependency of the domestic market with the others market. we observe that any events occurring in them, cause only small and statistically insignificant reactions in all stock exchange.

Finally, concerning the influences occurring among the remaining markets we must note the following:

- It appears that the New York market is shaped solely by the influence of domestic factors (USA) given that a shock originating domestically influences Dow Jones substantially but only for the first day after it is announced. The other markets do not appear to influence Dow Jones, since any influences are small and statistically insignificant.
- The DAX-30 index responds instantaneously to changes in domestic factors which complete their influence also within a day. From the foreign markets only the USA influences substantially the German market since all the other markets exert negligible and statistically insignificant influences.
- For the London market, it appears that it is considerably influenced by the New York stock exchange as well as the DAX-30 Index. These influences are absorbed within the day by the London stock exchange, so they last for as long as the domestic changes.
- The Japanese market reacts sharply to shocks originating in the New York market. The influences last and they are statistically significant for a two day period, in contrast with previous cases where influences lasted for a day at most.

Conclusions

This study offers a continuation of the research on the issue of financial markets growing interdependency, in the context of globalization. The empirical results reveal that both the long-run cointegrating relationships and the short-run dynamic linkages among major world financial markets are strengthened through time. The US global influence is noticeable on all major world financial markets. It also responds significantly to primarily domestic shocks. Furthermore, our findings suggest that the France stock market is strongly affected by all major stock Market.

If the results of this study are extended and contrasted with previous studies, they clearly suggest that financial market integration is time-varying. Further research might be taken towards this direction.

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